

RECOVERY OF ALCOHOLS IN AQUEOUS STREAM FROM STABILIZED PYROLYSIS OIL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT: The aqueous phase derived from Stabilized Pyrolysis Oil (SPO) and Stabilized Deoxygenated Pyrolysis Oil (SDPO) contains a complex mixture of water and valuable organics such as methanol, ethanol, and acetic acid. The recovery of these compounds represents a promising route for the valorization of pyrolysis side-streams. This study presents the simulation and optimization of a distillation system designed to recover light alcohols from aqueous streams derived from SPO and SDPO. Using a re-parametrized Non-Random Two-Liquid (NRTL) thermodynamic model implemented in COCO process simulation, a four-column distillation system was designed to selectively recover methanol and ethanol with purities of 99.99 wt% and 92.5 wt%, respectively, at high recovery rates (>95 %). Acetic acid recovery, though technically feasible, was found economically infeasible due to excessive energy demand. The study demonstrates the viability of valorizing pyrolysis aqueous phases through energy-optimized separation schemes.

Keywords: SPO aqueous, SDPO aqueous, process design, COCO process simulation, NRTL model.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced biofuels are crucial for meeting Europe's climate objectives and addressing global warming (1). By 2050, they have the potential to supply 14% of the world's transport fuel and 45% of the aviation fuel required globally. When produced sustainably, these biofuels could cut CO₂ emissions by approximately 21 gigatons (Gt) annually, leading to a significant reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (2). The FUEL-UP project (3), funded by the European Union, aims to advance bio-oil conversion into sustainable biofuels, specifically targeting the aviation and maritime sectors. The project integrates fast pyrolysis (FP) technology to produce bio-oils and subsequent stabilization and deoxygenation steps to produce high-quality fuels and chemicals. These steps are integrated within large-scale refining to ensure efficient transformation of all streams into advanced biofuels and chemicals.

Raw pyrolysis oil is highly oxygenated, acidic, and chemically unstable, requiring further upgrading prior to use (4,5,6). A common approach is two-step catalytic hydrotreatment. In the first step, Stabilized Pyrolysis Oil (SPO) is produced via mild hydrogenation, selectively removing reactive species such as aldehydes, ketones, and acids to improve stability. In the second step, Stabilized Deoxygenated Pyrolysis Oil (SDPO) is generated under more severe conditions using deep hydrodeoxygenation to remove most of the remaining oxygen (4,5,6,7). The resulting SDPO is a hydrocarbon-rich liquid with low acidity, high calorific value, and properties compatible with conventional fuels (5,6,7).

The products from both the SPO and SDPO processes are an organic phase and an aqueous phase (5,7). Aqueous phase from these processes is a complex mixture of water and various dissolved organic compounds, including alcohols (methanol, ethanol, propanol, and butanol), sugars (levoglucosan and others), carboxylic acids (mainly acetic and formic acid), furfural, guaiacol, and minor quantities of aldehydes and ketones (5,6,7). The aqueous phase is generally disposed of as a waste stream or potentially utilised as co-feed in biogas plants (3). However, given the composition of this mixture, it could be considered a valuable resource for producing various bio-based chemicals and fuels, though the

chemicals of interest are highly diluted in water. Therefore, up-concentration and purification are needed, which makes the process potentially economically challenging.

A common and industrially proven method for separating valuable compounds from chemical industry is conventional distillation. This technique uses differences in boiling points to separate components such as methanol, ethanol, and water. Although energy-intensive—especially when components form azeotropes—are present in low concentrations—it remains a reliable and easily scalable option in many bio-refining processes. Another approach is extractive distillation (8), where an organic solvent is added to help separate polar compounds like alcohols and acetic acid. After extraction, the solvent is evaporated and recycled, and the target compounds can be recovered. Azeotropic distillation is another option (9), in which water is removed by forming azeotropes with added entrainers. However, these solvent-based methods involve introducing a third compound (entrainer), which can reduce final product purity and add complexity to the process, especially in terms of heat integration and solvent regeneration.

Investigating the recovery of alcohols and other valuable compounds such as acetic acid and formic acid from the aqueous phase of SPO and SDPO via distillation is essential for assessing both the technical and economic feasibility of the process. This is particularly important given the low concentrations of these compounds, which may require substantial energy input for effective separation and purification. Process simulation plays a crucial role in enabling faster and more efficient design and optimization, thereby supporting feasibility assessments for chemical recovery. To ensure accurate simulation results, the thermodynamic models used should reliably represent the complex mixtures present in the aqueous phase of SPO and SDPO. In the present system, strong non-idealities in the liquid phase are likely, particularly due to the presence of azeotropic mixtures. Accordingly, advanced thermodynamic models are needed to properly describe the system. Activity coefficient models such as Non-Random Two-Liquids (NRTL) and UNIQUAC are considered the most suitable for describing vapor-liquid equilibrium (VLE), which is

critical for the design of thermal separation systems. However, the NRTL models implemented in both Aspen Plus and COCO (CAPE-OPEN to CAPE-OPEN) do not accurately reproduce the equilibrium data for most ternary mixtures involving water, C1–C4 alcohols (*i.e.*, methanol, ethanol, propanol, and n-butanol), and light carboxylic acids such as acetic acid and formic acid. Consequently, these models cannot be reliably employed for the design and scale-up of separation processes for organic compounds from the aqueous phase. The lack of accurate thermodynamic models thus represents a significant gap in the current literature.

Currently, BTG's process upgrades bio-oil in two steps: selective hydrogenation at mild conditions yields SPO, which is then deoxygenated at higher temperatures and moderate pressures to produce SDPO (3). In the FUEL-UP project, distillation system are selected as primary unit operation for recovery of valuable resource in the aqueous phases. The feedstocks investigated are aqueous phases from both SPO and SDPO, shipped to SINTEF labs by BTG. Experimental work has been conducted on a lab-scale distillation column, and the results have been used to support process simulations. However, the laboratory-scale studies themselves are not discussed in this paper.

The COCO simulation environment is a license-free (10), modular process simulation platform developed by AmsterCHEM. It provides a flexible framework for modeling and analyzing chemical processes, with full support for CAPE-OPEN standards. COCO integrated thermodynamic and unit operation packages offers a practical and transparent environment for process design and optimization, particularly in early-stage development and academic research. The platform allows users to define and simulate flowsheets involving multiple unit operations—such as distillation, extraction, heat exchange, and reactors—while incorporating custom thermodynamic models, including user-regressed NRTL and UNIQUAC formulations.

The presented work involves process design, modeling, and optimization to develop an efficient separation train for recovering value-added products from aqueous side streams, while aiming to reduce energy consumption and maximize product recovery. A feasibility assessment was conducted to recover specific key chemicals from aqueous streams from stabilized pyrolysis process and stabilized deoxygenated pyrolysis process. The core goals are:

- Developing a simulation using COCO-COFE process simulator to design a distillation system capable of separating high-value chemicals from aqueous side streams.
- Optimizing energy consumption within the distillation system, evaluating the recovery potential of key components.

2 PROCESS DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION

2.1 Thermodynamic model

The NIST database is used to retrieve experimental measurements for the regression of the thermodynamic model accounting for binary and ternary mixtures (11) gathers and resumes the combinations of binary and ternary mixtures, the number of data available for each of those, and the covered range for temperature, pressure, and composition. The activity-based model was then re-

tuned by SINTEF to enhance the predictive accuracy of the NRTL model.

The NRTL model has been regressed in Aspen PLUS V14 (licensed by SINTEF) using the Maximum Likelihood algorithm following the same procedure adopted in Gilardi et al. (12). Both temperature-independent (A_{ij}) and temperature-dependent (B_{ij}) binary coefficients are regressed, while the non-randomness coefficient is kept at a fixed value of 0.3 for all mixtures. Details on the theoretical background of the NRTL model and on binary interaction coefficients expressions are available in Renon and Prausnitz (13). The Modified Barker's algorithm is employed for model evaluation. For isothermal binary data, temperature (T) and liquid composition (x) are fixed, while pressure (P) and vapor composition (y) are calculated. For isobaric binary data, P and x are fixed, and T and y are computed. In the case of ternary data, both T , P , and x are specified, with y as the only output due to the additional degree of freedom. Model accuracy is assessed using relative deviations between experimental and predicted values.

The Average Relative Deviation (ARD) for the generic variable z (T , P , or y) is defined as:

$$ARD = \frac{1}{N_{data}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{data}} \left| \frac{z_{exp,i} - z_{mod,i}}{z_{exp,i}} \right|$$

2.2 The process design, modelling, and optimization

Process flowsheet of the distillation system for chemical recovery from the SPO aqueous phase (capacity of 3082 kg/h) and the SDPO aqueous phase (capacity of 3082 kg/h). Preliminary composition analysis of these samples indicates that the water content is relatively high (over 85 wt%). Among the organic compounds, ethanol, methanol, propanol, butanol, formic acid, and acetic acid are prominently present in both the SPO and SDPO aqueous samples—particularly ethanol, methanol, and acetic acid, which are found at concentrations ranging from 1 to 6 wt%. Therefore, the simulation focuses on these three key components. The SPO and SDPO aqueous streams are mixed and fed into a train of distillation columns, which are optimally designed to recover the target compounds with acceptable recovery rates and product purities.

The NRTL regress model established in section 2.1 has been used in the studies for process design, modelling, and optimization of recovering main components from aqueous phase of SPO, SDPO: ethanol, methanol, propanol, butanol, formic acid, and acetic acid. The simulation was carried out using the COCO process simulator. The process consists of three distillation columns in series and aims at recovering methanol and ethanol at commercial grade and one column for acetic acid recovery. The number of theoretical trays and the positioning of the feed are optimised in each column to find a balance between column sizes and energy requirements.

Figure 1: COCO flowsheet of the distillation system for methanol, ethanol, and acetic acid recovery from mixed SPO and SDPO aqueous phase.

The block flow diagram developed for the separation process is presented in Fig 1. In the first distillation column (Col1), a bulk separation is performed. Water and most of C3+ alcohols, formic, and acetic acid are recovered in the bottom, while the distillate is enriched in methanol and ethanol. Some water (~10-30%) will still be present in the distillate due to azeotropic nature of the ethanol-water mixture. In the second distillation column (Col2), the distillate of Col1 is treated to separate methanol (at commercial purity) from ethanol and water. Water will remain in the bottom together with ethanol. In the third column (Col3), ethanol is concentrated up to the azeotropic composition and recovered in the distillate. In the fourth column (Col4), the bottom product of Col1 is mixed with the water-rich residue from Col3 and is then treated to recover acetic acid at over 30 wt% purity in the bottom residue (boiling point 118 °C). Though, higher acetic acid purities can be achieved by extractive or azeotropic distillation.

Table I: Design specifications for each distillation column

Column	Specifications
Col1	- 99.5% recovery of ethanol (and close to 100% of methanol) on the top - 99.5% recovery of H ₂ O in the bottom.
Col2	- 99.99 vol% methanol purity in distillate - Residual methanol in the bottom 0.04 vol% (lowest methanol loss achievable)
Col3	- 95 vol% ethanol recovery in distillate. - 99.5 vol% recovery of 1-propanol in the bottom
Col4	- 30 wt% Acetic Acid purity in the bottom - Reflux ratio=5

The process was designed based on specific criteria outlined in Table I, with the objective of maximizing the recovery of ethanol, methanol, and acetic acid while achieving the highest possible product purities. The optimal number of theoretical trays and the feed stage location are determined to ensure a balanced trade-off between investment and operating costs. In general, increasing the number of trays leads to higher material requirements for column construction (thus higher CAPEX), but allows for lower energy consumption during operation. Conversely, reducing the number of trays decreases construction costs but increases energy demand. This optimization process must ensure

compliance with the process design specifications presented in Table 1. All four columns operate within a temperature range of 65°C to 115°C. Given these factors, each column is optimized by analyzing the reboiler duty as a function of the number of theoretical stages. During the optimization of one column, the configurations of the other columns are kept unchanged. The optimization sequence proceeds from Column Col1 to Column Col4. Column optimization is defined as the combined adjustment of tray number and feed stage location to minimize energy consumption for each reboiler, considering the primary objective of product quality:

- 99.9% recovery of methanol and 99.9 wt % methanol-rich stream purity;
- 95% recovery of ethanol, at azeotropic composition (95.6 wt%).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The predictive performance of the newly regressed NRTL model was compared with the original Aspen Plus and COCO implementations. The ARD in the vapor-phase composition was significantly reduced across all tested binary and ternary systems. The regressed model achieved ARD values below 10% for 78% of the considered mixtures and exceeded 20% for only one mixture (Data not shown here). Remarkably, substantial improvements were observed in binary mixtures containing formic and acetic acid, where the model outperformed the standard Aspen Plus formulation. The ARD values predicted equilibrium temperature and pressure are investigated. The model demonstrates excellent consistency, with 80% of the mixtures showing ARD values below 1% for temperature and below 5% for pressure (Data not shown here). These results confirm the robustness and enhance predictive reliability of the re-parameterized model for a wide range of systems. The list of all the regressed binary interaction parameters for the NRTL model used for process simulation in this work is showed in table II.

Table II. List of the regressed NRTL coefficients.

Com i ^(*)	Com j	A _{ij}	A _{ji}	B _{ij}	B _{ji}
H ₂ O	MeOH	2.73	-0.69	-617.2	172.9
H ₂ O	EtOH	3.45	-0.80	-586.0	246.1
H ₂ O	PropOH	5.44	-1.74	-861.1	576.4
H ₂ O	ButOH	13.11	-2.04	-3338.9	763.8
MeOH	EtOH	4.711	-2.31	-1162.2	483.8
MeOH	PropOH	0	0	19.55	-8.8
MeOH	ButOH	2.22	-1.51	-337.7	242.6
MeOH	AcAc	-0.93	-1.74	760.7	157.8
EtOH	PropOH	8.26	-9.72	-2846.6	3409.6
EtOH	ButOH	0	0	-85.2	128.5
PropOH	ButOH	-1.42	2.46	205.8	-451.7
PropOH	AcAc	0	0	-723.1	1212.3
ButOH	AcAc	2.01	0.82	-268.7	-897.0
EtOH	AcAc	44.77	-4.22	-15450	940.4
H ₂ O	FoAc	1.23	2.30	-922.1	-677.3
AcAc	FoAc	-19.4	-10.70	8365.8	3629.4
H ₂ O	AcAc	-6.34	9.404	2202.3	-3172.9
ButOH	FoAc	7.77	-38.94	-2738.0	12292.4

(*):Com: component, H₂O: Water, MeOH: Methanol, EtOH: ethanol, PropOH: propanol, ButOH: butanol, AcAc: Acetic acid, FoAc: formic acid

Table III: Boiler duty optimization of Column Col1

Test	Total tray of Col 1	Feed SPO position	Feed SDPO position	Boiler duty (kw)
T1-1	35	24	29	1980
T1-2	35	22	29	1981
T1-3	35	20	29	1981
T1-4	35	18	29	1981
T1-5	35	15	29	1982
T1-6	35	10	29	1982
T1-7	35	5	29	2735
T1-8	35	18	20	1152
T1-9	35	18	18	1065
T1-10	35	18	16	913
T1-11	35	18	12	868
T1-12	35	18	8	867
T1-13	35	22	12	907
T1-14	35	26	12	995
T1-15	35	14	12	885
T1-16	20	10	6	1125
T1-17	25	12	8	942
T1-18	30	15	10	890
T1-19	35	18	12	868
T1-20	40	20	12	848
T1-21	30	22	10	868

Capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operating expenditure (OPEX) are key considerations in the design of an efficient recovery system for valuable components from the aqueous phases of SPO and SDPO. In this context, optimizing the total number of theoretical stages (which directly impacts CAPEX) and minimizing energy consumption—primarily driven by reboiler duty (OPEX)—are essential to understand process feasibility. To achieve commercial-grade recovery of ethanol and methanol, Column Col1 plays a vital role in the distillation system to remove the bulk of the water and increase the concentration of target alcohols.

Table IV: The optimal conditions, energy requirements and recovery of key components for each column

	Col1	Col2	Col3	Col4
Feed_position 1	10 (SDPO)	18	17	12
Feed_position 2	22 (SPO)	-	-	-
Feed rate (kg/h)	6164 ⁽¹⁾	495	316	5706
Total number of stages	30	55	30	25
Cooler duty (kw)	2667	649	286	20429
Boiler duty (kw)	868	649	286	20428
Ethanol purity (%)	54,6 ⁽²⁾	-	92,5 ⁽²⁾	0,0
Ethanol recovery (wt%)	99,5 ⁽²⁾	-	94,5 ⁽²⁾	-
Methanol purity (%)	36,1 ⁽²⁾	99,9 ⁽²⁾	-	-
Methanol recovery (wt%)	99,5 ⁽²⁾	99,4 ⁽²⁾	-	-
Acetic purity (%)	2,1 ⁽³⁾	-	-	38,5 ⁽³⁾
Acetic recovery (wt%)	99,9 ⁽³⁾	-	-	84,4 ⁽³⁾

⁽¹⁾total feedrate of SPO and SDPO aqueous stream, ⁽²⁾at top product, ⁽³⁾at bottom product

Table III presents the results of the optimization study for Col1, where different combinations of total tray numbers and feed tray positions were tested to minimize reboiler duty. The configuration with 30 trays and feed positions 22 for SPO stream and 10 for SDPO stream (test T1-21) was found to be optimal, achieving the best case (boiler duty of 868 kW). Introducing feeds at inappropriate tray levels (e.g., from tests T1-1 to T1-7) led to a sharp increase in energy consumption (1980 –

2735 Kw) due to poor separation efficiency

The optimization procedure was similarly applied to the remaining distillation columns. Table IV summarizes the best-performing configurations for the recovery of ethanol, methanol, and acetic acid, based on variations in feed tray positions and the total number of trays for each column.

Figure 2: Temperature and liquid composition profiles for distillation column system at the optimal configuration

Column Col2, operated with a feed rate of 495 kg/h, 55 theoretical stages, and a feed position at stage 18, enables efficient separation of methanol from the ethanol–water mixture. Under these conditions, methanol is recovered with a purity of 99.9 vol% and a recovery rate of 99.4 wt%, meeting commercial AA-grade specifications. The corresponding reboiler and condenser duties are 649 kW. Column Col3 further concentrates ethanol–water mixture obtained from column Col2. Operating with 30 stages, a feed tray located at stage 17, and a feed rate of 316 kg/h, the column achieves an ethanol product purity of 92.5 wt% and a recovery of 94.5 wt%. The ethanol concentration is slightly lower than the theoretical maximum (95.6 wt%) achievable in the ethanol–water azeotropic mixture. This deviation may be attributed to the presence of propanol and butanol in the aqueous phase of the SPO and SDPO streams, which can influence the vapor–liquid equilibrium, as well as minor inaccuracies in the parameters of the regressed NRTL dynamic model. The energy requirements are relatively low, with boiler duty of 286 kW. Column Col4, tasked with recovering acetic acid, exhibits the most energy-intensive operation. Despite achieving a bottom

product purity of 38.5 wt% and recovery of 84.4 wt%, the required boiler duty exceeds 20400 kW, indicating a specific heat consumption of over 13 MJ/kg of recovered acetic acid. This is largely due to the low concentration (~2.1 wt%) of acetic acid in the feed of Col4 and its strong non-ideal interaction with water. The results reaffirm that acetic acid recovery by conventional distillation is technically possible but economically unjustifiable.

Fig. 2 provides a detailed overview of the internal temperature profiles and liquid–vapor composition distributions across the four distillation columns. These profiles offer valuable insights into the underlying separation mechanisms, azeotropic limitations, and component partitioning behaviors throughout the stages. In Column Col1, where the initial bulk separation takes place, the temperature increases from approximately 72 °C at the condenser to nearly 100 °C at the reboiler. This gradient aligns well with the boiling points of water and light alcohols. The liquid composition profile shows a clear enrichment of methanol and ethanol in the upper stages, while heavier compounds such as propanol, butanol, acetic acid, and formic acid together with water accumulate in the bottom section. The significant presence of acetic acid in the bottom stream reflects their low volatility and strong affinity for water. Remarkably, the concentrations of both ethanol and methanol decrease sharply after stage 20. However, the number of trays in Column Col1 was extended to 30 to mitigate this loss and ensure a near-complete recovery of these components. Column Col2 is dedicated to the purification of methanol to commercial AA-grade quality. The temperature across the trays ranges from approximately 64 °C to 78 °C. Methanol concentration increases sharply in the upper stages, reaching 99.9 wt% in the distillate, while water and ethanol are predominantly retained in the bottom product. This separation profile confirms the high efficiency of the column in producing high-purity methanol with minimal carryover of heavier alcohols, and highlights the excellent control of the cut point along the column. Column Col3 targets ethanol enrichment and operates at slightly higher temperatures (~76–82 °C). Both liquid and vapor profiles exhibit a plateau at 92.5 wt% ethanol. Column Col4, designed for acetic acid recovery, shows the steepest temperature gradient among all columns, with the bottom temperature approaching 103 °C. This highlights the significant energy required—over 20 MW—to evaporate water and concentrate acetic acid to a target level of 38.5 wt%. Although water (boiling point of 100 °C) and acetic acid (boiling point of 118 °C) do not form an azeotrope, their separation by conventional distillation is inherently difficult. This is primarily due to the narrow boiling point gap and the low relative volatility between the two components, particularly at high water concentrations. Under such conditions, substantial energy input are required to achieve the desired separation, often making simple distillation economically unattractive for recovering acetic acid. Collectively, the temperature and composition trends in Fig. 2 support the column design strategy, confirm the presence of azeotropic behavior, and highlight the importance of accurate thermodynamic modeling. These profiles also provide a useful diagnostic for further process improvements, such as implementing heat integration or considering hybrid separation options where appropriate—particularly for energy-intensive steps like acetic acid recovery.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusion is that there is potential for light alcohols recovery, mainly ethanol and methanol from SPO and SDPO aqueous phase, for applications in fuel blending and/or in the chemical industry. These alcohols can be effectively separated from water and other heavier compounds by means of 3 distillation columns. Indeed, high recovery rates of 99.9% for methanol and 94.5% for ethanol, along with product purities of 99.9 wt% and 92.5 wt%, respectively, can be achieved adopting a simple process layout made up of the distillation simulation on CoCo. On the other hand, the recovery of acetic acid seems not economical feasible, mainly due to their low concentration and to the intrinsic difficulty in their separation from water (strongly non-ideal mixtures and close boiling points).

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